

On the error involved in the determination of activation energy of solid state reactions by using Coats-Redfern method

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An attempt has been made to find out precisely the error involved in the determination of activation energy by Coats and Redfern method. We also consider the case of temperature dependent frequency factor. The findings have been tested by evaluating activation energies from theoretical as well as experimental thermogravimetry curves of solid state reactions.

Coats and Redfern¹ proposed a method for the analysis of non-isothermal kinetic data by combining the Arrhenius law with the equation for the rate in terms of α , the fractional conversion. As a result, one obtains the relationship,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = \frac{A}{\beta} f(\alpha) \exp(-E/RT) \quad (1)$$

where t is the time, A the frequency factor, β the constant heating rate, E the activation energy, R the universal gas constant and T the temperature at time t . For the reaction order (RO) model of reaction mechanism,

$$f(\alpha) = (1 - \alpha)^n \quad (2)$$

where n is the order of reaction. Integrating eqn. (1) we get,

$$\begin{aligned} g(\alpha) &= \frac{AE}{\beta R} \int_x^\infty \frac{\exp(-x')}{x'^2} dx' \\ &= \frac{AE}{\beta R} p(x) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

with $x = E/RT$. In logarithm form,

$$\ln g(\alpha) = \ln \frac{AE}{\beta R} + \ln p(x) \quad (4)$$

The scope of the present paper is to determine the error involved in the activation energy calculated from Coats-Redfern (CR) method. The error is determined as a function of the parameter E/RT in order to assess the range of applicability of CR method in kinetic studies. It is to be noted that CR method has been widely used for the determination of the kinetic parameters of solid state reactions.

Theory :

A difficulty in non-isothermal kinetic methods is that there is no exact analytical solution of $p(x)$ and therefore the solution cannot be expressed in a closed form, although

there exists several convergent series for its approximation with a high level of accuracy. In the present paper, the reference values of the temperature integral, $\int_0^1 \exp(-E/RT') dT'$ have been computed by using Urbanovici and Segal² approximation, so that

$$p(x) = \frac{\exp(-x)}{x^2} h(x) \quad (5)$$

where

$$h(x) = \frac{x^2 + 5.347x + 1.376}{x^2 + 7.347x + 10.069} \quad (6)$$

Let $p(x_a)$ is the approximation of the $p(x)$ function given by Coats and Redfern¹,

$$p(x_a) = \frac{\exp(-x_a)}{x_a^2} \left\{ 1 - \frac{2}{x_a} \right\} \quad (7)$$

where the subscript represents to an approximate value of x . However, the expression commonly used in the literature is the simplest and most popular form,

$$p(x_a) = \frac{\exp(-x_a)}{x_a^2} \quad (8)$$

leading to a linear correction.

Let us call $x_a = E_a/RT$, the apparent value of x obtained from the approximation of the $p(x)$ function. The error δ of x_a with respect to the true value of x can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= \frac{(E_a/RT) - (E/RT)}{(E/RT)} \times 100 \\ &= \frac{x_a - x}{x} \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{E_a - E}{E} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

By introducing the exact expression of $p(x)$ [eqn. (5)] into eqn. (3), we have

$$\ln g(\alpha) = \ln \frac{A_a R}{E_a \beta} - x - 2 \ln x + \ln h(x) \quad (10)$$

Using the above procedure together with the Coats-Redfern method, we get from eqns. (8) and (3),

$$\ln g(\alpha) = \ln \frac{A_a R}{E_a \beta} + 2 \ln T - \frac{E_a}{RT} \quad (11)$$

Now by differentiating eqn. (10) with respect to $1/T$, we get,

$$\frac{\partial \ln g(\alpha)}{\partial (1/T)} = -\frac{E}{R} - \frac{2}{T} + \frac{\partial \ln h(x)}{\partial (1/T)} \quad (12)$$

Again by differentiating eqn. (11) with respect to $1/T$, we can write,

$$\frac{\partial \ln g(\alpha)}{\partial (1/T)} = -\frac{E_a}{R} - 2T \quad (13)$$

From eqns. (12) and (13) one gets,

$$\frac{E_a}{R} - \frac{E}{R} = \frac{\partial \ln h(x)}{\partial (1/T)} \quad (14)$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} \delta &= \frac{E_a - E}{E} \times 100 \\ &= -\frac{\partial \ln h(x)}{\partial x} \times 100 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

We can see that the percentile proportional error in the determination of the activation energy by the CR method is dependent only on the parameter $x = E/RT$.

Results and Discussion

The errors in x obtained from the CR method are shown in Table 1 as a function of the values of x taken as accurate ones for computing $p(x)$. It is evident from Table 1 that the activation energy can be determined from the CR method with an accuracy better than 5%.

Table 1. Errors in activation energy (E) calculated from the CR approximation as a function of $x = E/RT$ for different values of r

$x = E/RT$	5	10	20	50	60	80	100
$r = 0$	-4.74	-1.47	-0.421	-0.074	-0.052	-0.030	-0.019
$r = 0.5$	14.44	8.05	4.40	1.89	1.59	1.206	0.971
$r = 1$	5.10	3.32	1.99	0.908	0.769	0.588	0.476
$r = -0.5$	-13.33	-6.09	-2.82	-1.06	-0.872	-0.647	-0.514
$r = -1$	-22.38	-10.76	-5.22	-2.04	-1.69	-1.27	-1.01

In order to check the above finding we performed the kinetic analysis of theoretical thermogravimetry (TG) curves generated by Zuru *et al.*³. The activation energies as calculated by CR method are collected in Table 2 together with the input values of E , A and n . Again the CR method

is also applied to determine the activation energies from TG curves of the complexes Cu(BSTCZ)(HCOO), Cu(BSTCZ)(CH₃CH₂COO), where BSTCZ stands for 1,5-bis-salidenethiocarbohydrazone (hereafter denoted by complex-1 and complex-2 respectively) reported by Prasad and Singh⁴. In Table 3, we report the activation energies of both the complexes as calculated by CR method together with the kinetic parameters of the complexes obtained by a rigorous method of curve fitting⁵.

It is evident from Tables 2 and 3 that in general, the errors incurred in the determination of activation energy with the aid of CR method are in fair agreement with those forecasted in Table 1, where in the case of experimental TG curves we take the values of E as determined by the curve fitting method as the standard one.

Table 2. Errors in the activation energies of some numerically computed TG curves with $\beta = 0.083^{\circ} \text{C/s}$ as calculated with CR approximation

Input values of kinetic parameters				
E_{in}	Z_{in}	n_{in}	E_{CR}	$\Delta = \frac{E_{CR} - E_{in}}{E_{in}} \times 100$
kcal mol ⁻¹	$\times 10^{11} \text{ s}^{-1}$		kcal mol ⁻¹	
20.02	1.67	1	19.94	-0.400
20.02	1.67	2	19.96	-0.300

Table 3. The errors in the activation energies of TG curves of some copper complexes ($\beta = 0.1667^{\circ} \text{C/s}$) as calculated in the CR approximation

Complex	Curve fitted values of kinetic parameters			E_{CR} kcal mol ⁻¹	$\Delta = \frac{E_{CR} - E_{ct}}{E_{CR}} \times 100$
	E_{ct} kcal mol ⁻¹	Z_{ct} s ⁻¹	n_{ct}		
1	39.12	3.67×10^{13}	2.33	39.00	-0.307
2	37.44	1.50×10^{11}	2.42	36.57	-2.32

Finally, we come to the case of temperature dependent frequency factor⁶⁻⁸,

$$A = A_r T^r \quad (A_r = \text{constant}; r = \text{constant}) \quad (16)$$

In this case, eqn. (3) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} g(\alpha) &= \frac{A_r}{\beta} \left(\frac{E}{R}\right)^{r+1} \int_x^{\infty} \frac{\exp(-x')}{x'^{r+2}} dx' \\ &= \frac{A_r}{\beta} \left(\frac{E}{R}\right)^{r+1} p_r(x) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Following Urbanovici and Segal², we write,

$$p_r(x) = \frac{\exp(-x)}{x^{r+2}} h_r(x) \quad (18)$$

with

$$h_r(x) = \frac{x+1}{x+3+r} \quad (19)$$

so that $r \neq 0$, eqn. (15) becomes

Note

$$\Delta = \frac{r}{x} - \frac{\partial \ln h_r(x)}{\partial x}$$

(20)

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In Table 1, we also tabulate Δ for some non-zero values of r (Dollimore *et al.*⁶). It is seen that Δ is negative for negative values of r whereas it is positive for positive values of r . Again value of Δ for a particular negative value of r is greater than that for positive r .

Conclusion : We conclude that CR method investigated here leads to reasonably good results. Therefore, this approximation can safely be used for the determination of activation energy for solid state reactions.

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